

CAUGHT BETWEEN THE EXTREMES: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF STATE OWNED NEWS CHANNEL AND A PRIVATE NEWS CHANNEL

¹Muhammad Umer Azim, ²Zaheer Hussain, ³Azhar Munir Bhatti ⁴Muhammad Iqbal
⁵Muhammad Nadeem Chohan

ABSTRACT

A comparative study of Pakistani electronic media discourses was done in this article. Different news channels project different ideologies and it was needed to be studied. The qualitative paradigm was used to do Critical Discourse Analysis using Ideological Square model given by Van Dijk. The recordings of a day's bulletin were analyzed for both the privately owned news channel and the state owned news channel. It was found out that both the channels were strictly following their ideologies and following the principles of 'emphasize positive about Us', 'emphasize negative about Them', 'de-emphasize negative about Us' and 'de-emphasize positive about Them'. State owned news channel is following pro government ideology and privately owned news channel is following antigovernment and pro-Imran ideology.

Keywords: *electronic media discourses, Critical Discourse Analysis, Van Dijk, Ideological Square model*

1. Introduction

Media discourse means a mediated interaction between media houses in the form of written or spoken text with the absent or non-present viewer, listener or reader. The researcher in this article is interested in Pakistani electronic media and specifically the news channels discourses in presenting news. These news media discourses in the present world are usually the only source of information for the common audience and they take almost everything presented as news, the truth. So these media houses are becoming the sources of opinion making and creation of power structure by creating knowledge that can direct a certain kind of behavior.

¹University of Management & Technology Lahore Pakistan

²National University of Modern Languages Lahore Campus

³Higher Education Department, Punjab, Pakistan

^{4,5}University of Management of Technology Lahore, Pakistan

A great variety of news channels is another issue for spreading the multiple ideologies among the masses. The news channels usually do not agree with each other and resultantly there is no single truth created for the audience and sometimes news are not matched with each other at all. It is because 'the infusion' which is the process of collection, selection and interpretation of news and 'the diffusion' which is the process of dissemination and circulation of news in Pakistan is not reliable. Infusion involves ideologies of news channels. Diffusion is propagation of this ideology through mass media. If one watches the news bulletins, specially the national news, on different news channels sometimes it seems that they are talking about two different countries because none of their news are corresponding or matching. This gives researcher the feeling that these news channels have their own agendas and they want to promote, create and sustain a certain ideology to meet their covert goals. To establish or reject this notion a comparative study of state owned news channel and a private news channel is planned. It has analyzed their one day bulletins to compare different national news projected on them and the airtime given to specific news and what and how 'truths' are shared that can direct the behavior of the audience. For this purpose, Critical Discourse Analysis will be conducted by using Van Dijk's 'Ideological Square' model.

The tradition of Discourse Analysis (DA) is very old. It is very broad field and under this umbrella term there are a number of sub-fields and disciplines. DA means 'the study of language in use'. It has not much concern with 'usage' which can be the work of 'parsing'. In 'parsing' of sentences are divided into grammatical categories. DA goes beyond that 'parsing' because it considers context in which particular language is used. The context is of absolute importance is the successful execution of DA.

Discourse can be either done on spoken or written language. There are some who make distinctions between 'spoken discourse' and 'written discourse' (Jackson & Stockwell, 2011) but many consider them as one. The words, phrases and clauses have their meaning but they can only be understood by studying them in relation to their co-text, the words that surround them and their context, the real world situation in which these words are used.

DA is considered as interdisciplinary. Researchers adopt and adapt its theories and frameworks to match their particular disciplines. Sociology, literature, education, theology and many other disciplines use its approaches to serve their purposes of research.

Discourse analysis is becoming important as it is a relatively new way of looking at the discourses. It looks at the language use in creating; power relations, new realities, change societal values, and identities. The language is part of culture and all cultures are different and the use of language and vocabulary is also different. This diversity requires unique modeling and methods to judge the power relations in a particular language discourse. One limitation of DA is its models and frameworks are not perfectly applicable in The East because most of the researches in DA are done in the West. These frameworks are needed to be adapted and their standards of judgment are needed to be revised to suit the local culture.

Discourse Analysis has a special development in the form of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA). CDA emerged as discipline in 1990s with influential researchers like Norman Fairclough, Teun Van Dijk, and Ruth Wodak. Their contribution to the field of CDA was of seminal nature. Each of these critical discourse analysts has developed his own theories and analytical frameworks which are unique. Each of these analytical frameworks have sound philosophical basis and offer features that are applicable to certain field. Van Dijk started journal of CDA entitled ‘Discourse and Society’ in 1990 and later published many books. CDA focuses on the macro-structures to study the cultural and ideological meaning. It also studies the use of language in reproducing power in society.

CDA is also applied to multidisciplinary fields. Text and talk is the subject of CDA but different disciplines require development of specific field based analytical frameworks (Van Dijk, 2009). There are multiple analytical frameworks available for the researchers in CDA (Wodak and Meyer 2009). The study of complex social phenomena made CDA a multi-methodological approach (Wodak and Meyer 2009). According to Fairclough the aim of CDA is to “systematically explore the opaque relationship of causality and determine between a) discursive practices, events, and texts, and b) wider social and cultural structures, relations and processes” (p.132).

The purpose of this introduction is to set the background of the study which will focus on the comparative study of two Pakistani news channels using the framework of CDA. In the next part of the article, there is an overview of major theories and approaches which helped in developing the models for the analysis of text and talk. It is helpful in deciding upon the usage of the most suitable framework for the study.

2. Literature Review

This part reviews the theories, approaches and analytical tools developed by the proponents of CDA. The most important critical discourse analysts are Fairclough, Van Dijk, and Wodak. They presented their theories and developed their models and frameworks. The models and analytical frameworks are discussed briefly in this section.

2.1 Social Theory of Discourse

This theory has linguistic orientation and it focuses on the analysis of political and social events. This theory declares discourse as a social practice responsible for the establishment of power relations among different entities of the society. Fairclough (1992) states “Language use in society is a form of social practice rather than individual activity” (p. 63). The notion establishes the strong relationship between power, ideology and discourse. Fairclough (1992) proposed that there are 3 principles of this social theory of discourse. First, discourse is both constitutive and constituted; it contributes in constructing social structure. Second, social practice leads to social identities and establish relationship among different classes of social setups. Third, the system of knowledge and ideology of the society is the product of social practice.

2.1.1. Dialectical-Relational Approach (Three-dimensional model)

Using the theory discussed above, Fairclough (1992), developed a three-dimensional model in CDA which consists of text, discursive practice and social practice. The text is important because it links with the social practice through discursive practice. Discursive practice is the production, distribution and consumption of the text and the text is shaped by the social practice. This model studies the process of meaning making to establish the power relations and other social phenomena like inequality, gender, ethnicity, etc.

2.2. Theory of Ideology

This theory has multiple approaches and its basic purpose is to form many ideological notions and consumptions. Ideologies mostly capture the thinking of a social group which represents the social features of a set of people in society having identity, aims, customs, ethics, status and sources (Van Dijk, 1995). So, cognition and social factors, both are originated out of an

ideology. Ideologies are always flourished due to cognition, discourse and social factors. Van Dijk (1995) believed that social cognition is developed because of the common socio-cultural understanding of a particular group and their culture. For example, females mostly propagate the ideas regarding abortion, positive activities and male clichés resultantly develops feminist ideology. A particular ideology related to a group is developed due to the processing of social information and this processing needs a long time to be effective enough (Van Dijk, 1995).

In ideological representations the difference is created through ‘us’ and ‘them’, where ‘us’ represent all that is taken as positive and ‘them’ represent all that is negative or bad (Van Dijk, 1995). Cognitive functions are the part of ideologies which organize, monitor and control behaviors of a social group. Every behavior is the result of ideology and is accompanied by experience referred as models. These experiences or models influence the various acts of human life.

2.2.1. Van Dijk’s Ideological Square

The theory of ideology presented in the preceding paragraphs leads to Van Dijk’s (2000) framework of ideological square or conceptual square. He developed four basic points to facilitate ideological analysis to define different ideological stances. The four principles are as follows:

- Emphasize positive things about Us
- Emphasize negative things about Them
- De-emphasize negative things about Us
- De-emphasize positive things about Them

These four principles are significant for the analysis of wider contextual strategies. These strategies include positive self-presentation, mentioning all good about oneself, and negative other-presentation, mentioning all that is bad about others. Self-presentation deals with the actions of individuals who are the members of a social group while emphatically portraying conforming or representative ideological concepts. Positive self-representation emphasizes positive behavior as in saying positive things about Us and hiding all that is negative. Negative other-presentation

emphasizes what negative behavior as in saying negative things about ‘them’ and hiding all that is positive.

2.2.2. Van Dijk’s Socio-cognitive Approach

This approach defines inter-relationship of cognition, discourse and society. The theory combines three fields; text linguistics, cognitive sciences and psychology. It takes textual analysis from text linguistics, model of memory from psychological and ‘frame’ from cognitive sciences. According to this approach access to power in the society is through the control different dimensions of discourse. An important element here is the K-device, which is the knowledge of the societal and individual elements. This knowledge and its effective use lead to the acquisition of power (Van Dijk, 2005).

2.3. Wodak’s Discourse-Historical Approach (DHA)

DHA is mostly influenced by Frankfurt School’s critical theory as it focuses the political aspect of discourse in society. This theory is helpful in revealing the ideologies in discourse and language used by the people in power. Wodak’s concept of critique (Reisigl and Wodak, 2009) justifies the validity and abstraction regarding some interpretations, which were criticized earlier. Aspects of critique are as follows:

1. Text or discourse-immanent critique: It focuses on the inconsistencies in the text itself.
2. Socio-diagnostic critique: It deciphers the discursive practices used as manipulative strategies considering the context and other societal structures of a particular society or group.
3. Future-related prospective critique: It helps in improving the communication by identifying the barriers of communication and proposing the strategies to minimize them.

DHA proposed six strategies which can help to gauge the ideological positioning. These strategies are; 1) nomination, 2) prediction, 3) argumentation, 4) perspectivisation, 5) intensification and 6) mitigation. This approach combines observation, theory and method to study discourse. But there is lack of systematic framework of evaluation which is its limitation.

After viewing the relevant and important theories, methods and frameworks used in CDA in this section the researcher decided in favor of Van Dijk's Ideological Square model. This model or framework is used by the researcher in this research. The presentation of the news on state owned channel and privately owned channel will be analyzed according to this model. This model serves the purpose of this article perfectly as the study is searching for hidden ideologies behind the specific news and specific presentation of the news on the electronic media. The researcher wants to see how the concept of *Us* and *Them* changes as the television news channel is changed and how this concept of *Us* and *Them* lead TV channels to select their news and present their news to their respective audience. This model is used by Pasha (2011) to study the Egyptian newspapers portrayal of ideology of Islam. It took news presented in the newspapers as its data and found that Muslim brotherhood was treated as 'Them' and their good was de-emphasized. Poorembrahim and Zarei (2013) used it to study the relationship of language and ideology. They studied 'image of Islam' in 'newspaper headlines' of the most circulated newspapers of America and Britain. They found negative representation of Islam. Ahmadian and Farahani (2014) also used this model to study ideological differences projected in the Iranian newspapers and American newspapers on topic of Iranian nuclear program. They found contradicting ideologies and prejudice among countries.

3. Methodology

It is a qualitative research in the field of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA). The research is conducted to analyze and surface the ideology of different news channels, a state owned news channel and a privately owned news channel, through the use of CDA.

3.1.Data Source

Recordings of two news channels of their major bulletins in a day were selected for the analyses. The day was chosen randomly through drawing a folded piece paper from seven pieces of folded papers so that researcher bias can be handled, the day selected was Sunday 15th January, 2017. The recorded bulletins were taken because they represent more stable stance of news channels. Live streaming can have some superfluous or momentary ideologies to present but the research in hand is interested in more stable stance or ideology of the news channels.

There was only one state owned news channel so choice was obvious. There are many privately owned news channels in Pakistan but two news channels are very popular and often compete to become the top rated news channel of Pakistan. Here one is little pro state and second is otherwise so the one is not pro state is chosen for comparison.

There is only one news bulletin on the state owned news channel at 9:00 pm and on the selected day the length of this bulletin was 59 minutes. State owned channel is the oldest news channel and its viewership is also maximum and the tradition of telecasting news at 9 is well established and people wait for the bulletin on this time. This time is also convenient for most of the people as institutions and organizations are mostly closed. But the important factor is majority has been 'trained' to watch the news at nine because of its long and well established tradition. Following the same tradition privately owned news channels also broadcast their major bulletins at 9. But privately owned channels also have their headlines every hour and bulletins every three hours. For the study, two bulletins of 6pm and 9pm were taken as they are the most watched bulletins and they also summarize the day's proceedings. There is a lot of repetition even in these two bulletins. Bulletin of 6 pm is of 30 minutes and bulletin of 9 pm is of 31 minutes and 20 seconds so time is almost the same.

3.2. Data Analysis

Data analysis is done using Van Dijk's Ideological Square model which has following points which can be observed in the data for analysis:

- Emphasize positive things about Us
- Emphasize negative things about Them
- De-emphasize negative things about Us
- De-emphasize positive things about Them

3.3. Delimitation

Only national news are considered for analysis. International and sports news are not considered for the analysis in this study.

4. Analysis

The bulletins considered have little in common as far as national news are concerned and the major strategy is ‘de-emphasizing the positive things about Them’. Although all other three were used but looking at the macro arrangement of bulletins ‘de-emphasize positive things about Them’ seems dominant. Second is ‘Emphasizing negative things about Them’ and third is Emphasizing positive things about Us and least use is ‘de-emphasize negative things about Us’.

There were around 15 national news items in bulletin of privately owned news channel and around 25 national news items in state owned news channel but only a couple of news are similar. The major focus of the article will be on one of them as the second was about army chief which is a non-political news.

The only news that was same on both the channels was about the increase of petrol prices by the government and almost all the techniques are used by both the channels in presenting the news.

Privately owned channel presented the news in sad tone and declared as destroying the happiness of Pakistan’s win against Australia in cricket and beautiful weather. “*hakomat ne Australia se jeet ka maza kirkira kar dia*” (The government has sabotaged the joy of winning against Australia). So the negative words are clearly visible here which are presenting ‘emphasize negative things about Them’. The speech of federal minister is telecast live while announcing the increase. Only little redeeming feature is the declaration of no raise in the prices of kerosene oil and light diesel which were also shown on the television screen. But next part of the news is clearly emphasizing the negative about the government and that is “*awam ne izafa mustarad kar dia*” (The public defied the increase). The people rejected the increment in petrol prices and to prove their point they have shown the interviews of 4 people (2 in 6 pm news bulletin and 2 in 9pm bulletin) declaring this increase as unacceptable and they demanded from the government to take back this decision. They declared it as extra burden on the poor people who are already suffering from high inflation in the country. Live interviews with the people made the reaction of people more authentic and convincing.

State owned channel presented it in an interesting way ‘emphasizing positive things about Us’ by beginning it stating all that is positive. *“Aalmi mandi mein izafay ke bawajood hakomat ne diesel or mitti k tail ki qeemtain barqarar rakhin... hakomat awam ko relief dene k liye 2 arab 75 crore ki subsidy bardasht karey gi”* (Despite the increase in international market, the prices of diesel and kerosene oil are not increased....The government is bearing the subsidy of 2.7 billion rupees for public relief). It is suggested as some big miracle that government has just increased the price that is very little and suffered hugely by providing subsidy to the common people. The minister said that kerosene oil and light diesel oil are used by poor people so they are given relief and no increase in their prices is suggested. Only half of what Oil & Gas Regulatory Authority (OGRA) suggested for petrol is recommended in case of petrol. So people should be happy that government has burdened itself and provided relief to the people. No comments from other political parties or public were included suggesting ‘de-emphasize negative thing about Us’. It was told that the oil prices in Pakistan are cheaper than any neighboring country so people of Pakistan should be thankful to their sitting government.

This news on the increment of petrol is the defining feature and reveals the ideologies of the two news channels. Privately owned news channel is clearly antigovernment and used all the techniques of news discourse to highlight the negatives in the government, while the state owned channel clearly supports the government and presents everything that is positive about Us and everything that is negative about Them. State owned news channel showed only the success of the government and de-emphasize what is negative about Us.

Second news which was same on both the channels was about the Chief of Army Staff’s contact to the President of Afghanistan to condole the terrorist attack in Afghanistan. Most of the material of the news was same as there was no political agenda behind and both the channels want to maintain good relations with army.

Third news which was not related to social news can be included because both the channels talked about weather. Privately owned channel used even weather to criticize the government as they were not able to provide relief to the people who were stuck on the roads because of the heavy snowfall. There was no proper arrangement to clear the roads and people in Chaman and Khojak Top were stuck for two days and the relief process was very slow. Same kinds of news were shared

about 'Galyat' and Quetta. Quite a good amount of airtime is provided to discuss this important issue. So emphasizing negative things about Them.

But state owned news channel has a rosy picture all around with little mentioning of problems associated just as a routine, nothing to worry about attitude. So de-emphasizing negative things about Us.

Privately owned news channel has almost all the news that are highlighting one or the other weaknesses of the government. The selection of news is surfacing their ideology. They are supporting all that is antigovernment. Important air time is given to Imran Khan's rally in DG Khan, area of South Punjab. The rally was highlighted and glamourized to mock the performance of the government. If opposition parties were able to gather such big crowds then it is self-evident that government is not performing well. The love and popularity of Imran Khan is highlighted among the people by playing songs and narrating interesting facts. The speech of Imran Khan was given good time and all that was negative about government and the ruling family was broadcast through the mouthpiece of Imran Khan. This saved the skin of the news channel but served its purpose. Corruption of government and panama leaks were highlighted. The words used to talk about the rally were positive and showing diversity of attendance and enthusiasm of rally. This suggests emphasizing positive things in Us along with emphasizing negative things in Them.

A minister of government was given less than a minute to defame Imran Khan and that too was presented objectively. It was just to show the fear existing among the ruling party. Otherwise there was no substance in that news. Through this the channel tried to balance its stance but it was too small to convince the audience of their objectivity regarding government and opposition, especially Pakistan Tehreek e Insaf (PTI).

Privately owned news channel criticized Sindh government for not processing the request of extension in the jurisdiction of rangers in Karachi. Antigovernment stance was projected by interviewing PTI's representative and Pak Sarzmeen Party (PSP) representative who severely criticized this action of Sindh government. They declared it as a failure of Sindh government and hinted on the hidden agenda of Sindh government behind this delay. No government official was taken online. Only news was shared that Chief Minister had decided to discuss the matter in cabinet

meeting, which was due next day. It shows lack of planning on the part of the Sindh government in particular and federal government in general.

Privately owned news channel pointed out many issues of mismanagement and bad governance emphasizing negative things in Them. Here some of them are mentioned. The kite flying is still going on in Lahore despite its ban a number of years ago. Crack downs are still in progress to stop kite flying after so many years. Quaid's birthplace in Karachi is surrounded by dirty water and waste of all kinds. Government failed to even provide good services to important monuments like these. Chained worker was rescued from Sialkot's factory. He was chained for more than two and a half months, what was the law enforcing agencies doing? Fire brigade office in Nazimabad Karachi was turned into marriage hall because all the fire trucks are out of order. The last line of the news was a grim criticism stating 'don't call this fire station if your house is on fire it's a marriage hall only'. *"agar aag lag jai tu yahan call karne ki zaroorat nahin, ye shadi hall hai"*. Another leader in opposition is given air time because it talks against the government policies of curriculum development and threatens to launch a protest or movement against government to counter these changes. Opposition leader is quoted saying that Prime Minister is behaving like the Minister of Punjab only and Chief Minister of Punjab is badly neglecting South Punjab. He criticized government for taking huge loans and telling lies.

This concludes the analysis of bulletins of privately owned news channel. Now the news of state owned news channel will be analyzed.

Apart from those three news, there were number of news presented in the bulletin we could divide them in two broad categories. First, anti-Imran propaganda and other was engagements of different federal and provincial ministers and some divergent news.

So anti-Imran propaganda is based on emphasizing negative things in Them. Information minister was included in the bulletin just because she talked negatively about Imran Khan. *"Jalson mein barhkain hanknain ke bajai adalton mein sabot dein" ... "Nawaz Sharif ke hasad nai Imram Khan ko zehni mareez bana diya ... aik bhi ilzam sabit nahin kar sake"*. She declared Imran Khan as psycho and jealous of Prime Minister. She proved that Imran Khan is a failure. Same is done by the Advisor to the Prime Minister in his address to a rally in Naushehra. He declared Imran Khan as hypocrite and said that many of his old friends were deserting him because of that. People

have seen the politics of Imran Khan which is based on lies only and so on. Good airtime is given to Chief Minister Punjab who met a number of government officials and presented a nice picture of developing Pakistan. He also implicitly criticized the attitude of opposition, especially Imran Khan.

Second part was based on emphasizing positive things in Us. Many ministers are shown a lot of good work in the field. Rural development program was going on successfully, Benazir Income Support Program was made transparent and efficient, Educationists were given motorcycles to get motivation, minorities are more secure and happy in Pakistan, Sikh minority students were given laptops on the direction of Chief Minister, Kissan Relief Package is doing wonders for the farmers, Islamabad Express Way will soon be completed and it will be a big relief to the people of twin cities, two days workshop for physically challenged people, Pakistan performed well in Colombo Exhibition, and last but not the least, Prime Minister of Pakistan will attend the Annual meeting of World Economic Forum and will be projecting a very positive image of Pakistan.

So here the analysis is done on the basis of selected criterion.

1. Results

The news on the increase in price of petrol is the defining feature and reveals the ideologies of the two news channels. Privately owned news channel is clearly antigovernment and used all the techniques of news discourse to highlight the negatives in the government, while the state owned channel clearly supports the government and presents everything that is positive about Us and Everything that is negative about Them. State owned news channel showed only the success of the government and de-emphasize what is negative about Us.

The privately owned news channel clearly antigovernment and pro Imran Khan. It is suggested by almost all the news analyzed above. This news channel provided a lot of air time to Imran Khan and his party. All the people who are against the government are given air time. It has deliberately not picked the news which was projecting positive things in Them. All the news which were going against Imran Khan, were also not picked so de-emphasize negative things about Us. Overall ideology of the privately owned news channel is quite clearly observable.

State owned news channel's ideology is also very visible through the use of all the principals. The channel has deliberately avoided all that is negative using de-emphasize negative things about Us. They have self-defined criterion to include a news item or not to include a news item. They mostly used the principal of emphasizing positive about Us and are successful. It is concluded that the audience of both the channels will be satisfied if they are not switching the channel because both the channels strictly follow their ideology and promote the same in their viewers. But the disparity between the channels is alarming. There can be difference of opinion but having only one or two news that are similar, rings a very negative bell. There should be some standardization or structure of news bulletin prescribed. The bulletins should have common news and other structural commonalities.

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